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Analysis of the Influence of Unsteady Flow on the Characteristics of NACA0009 Hydroprofile Under Cavitation Conditions

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Understanding cavitation phenomena is fundamental for improving the design and efficiency of all types of hydraulic machinery and fluid-mechanical systems. This research provides an additional contribution to the unsteady numerical simulation of the NACA0009 hydroprofile, truncated to 90% of its original length, in order to check and confirm its various hydrodynamic characteristics in cavitating conditions, including pressure pulsations. Numerous simulations were performed for different attack angles of the profile under constant cavitation number and constant flow velocity, thus expanding the scope of analysis of pressure, lift, and drag coefficients. Some of the numerical results were verified by the available experimental data and compared with other published results. In addition to quantitative indicators for each flow condition, a visualization of cavitation cloud is also provided, showing better insight into the interaction of fluid and structure.

Keywords: Cavitation, Unsteady Numerical Simulations, NACA0009 Hydroprofile, Hydrodynamic Characteristics

1. Introduction

Cavitation within hydraulic machines presents a very complex phenomenon that significantly affects the change in operating characteristics. The presence of cavitation in systems disrupts fluid flow in the zone of impeller blades, impairs the stability of fluid flow, causes damage to the flow tract structure, and decreases the coefficient of machine efficiency. Due to its importance, over the past decades, numerous research teams have carried out comprehensive experimental and numerical studies of cavitation in the fluid flow around hydroprofiles.

In the manuscript [1,2], the theory of calculating the drag and lift forces has been formulated and validated with experimental results. Dependences of these forces on the cavitation coefficient were established in [3], and the influence of gravitational force on the shape of the cavitation

cloud that is forming at the area of the profile surface is studied in [4]. Different types of cavitation that occur along a profile have been classified [5], and advanced numerical models have been developed to study the cavitation phenomenon with a reduced need for expensive experiments [6 - 12]. The relationship between the cavitation coefficient and the oscillation frequency of the hydro profile has been studied in [13], as well as the influence of cavitation on the dynamic characteristics of the hydro profile [14]. Previous simulations have included steady-state [15] and unsteady conditions [9, 12] applied to two-dimensional [12, 16] and three-dimensional hydroprofiles [10, 12, 17].

Compared to previous research, which studied steady-state numerical simulations, this study conducted unsteady numerical simulations of water flow around an isolated NACA0009 profile for various pitch angles. This approach enabled the analysis of dynamic changes in the flow field that arise as a result of cavitation, including pressure pulsations, phenomena that steady-state simulations cannot consider. Simulations were conducted for a constant cavitation number, static pressure at the outlet, and inlet flow velocity. As a result, the values of the pressure coefficient C_p , drag coefficient C_D , lift coefficient C_L , visualizations of the shape of the cavitation cloud, and the distribution of static pressure values over time for a single point positioned behind the hydroprofile were obtained. The validation of the simulation results for a profile rotation angle of 2.5° relies on previous experimental and numerical data [15,18,19].

2. Methodology

Within this research, a unsteady simulation was performed around a single two-dimensional NACA0009 profile truncated to 90% of its nominal length, throughout 0.35 s with the following attack angles of analyzed: $\alpha \in \{-16^\circ, -12^\circ, -8^\circ, -4^\circ, -2.5^\circ, 0^\circ, 2.5^\circ, 4^\circ, 8^\circ, 12^\circ, 16^\circ\}$.

To validate the applied model, special attention was given to the angle of attack $\alpha=2.5^\circ$ for which the results of numerical simulation were compared with data from previous experimental and numerical studies [15,18,19]. As a result of the simulations, the average values of the drag coefficient C_D , the lift coefficient C_L , the distribution of the pressure coefficient C_p along the profile, and the visualization of the shape of the cavitation cloud were obtained. During the simulations, as an indicator of the unsteadiness of the flow and pulsations related to the cavitation process, the change in pressure over time was monitored at a point P located 5 mm behind the flow-obstructed profile which is 100 mm in length, on the same longitudinal axis as the profile center of gravity.

In order to make the simulation as reliable as possible, the initial conditions were adopted from the experiment [18] and numerical simulation [15]. At the entrance to the flow domain, a constant water velocity $v = 20$ m/s was defined, while at the outlet cross-section, a constant static pressure of $p = 165216$ Pa was defined, which corresponds to a cavitation coefficient $\sigma = 0.81$. The cavitation coefficient is calculated according to expression (1):

$$\sigma = \frac{p - p_v}{\rho \frac{v^2}{2}} \quad (1)$$

Where p is the pressure downstream of the flow profile, ρ is the water density, and v is the water velocity. The fluid temperature is $t = 17^\circ\text{C}$, the Reynolds number is $\text{Re} \approx 2 \cdot 10^6$, and the turbulence intensity is $I = 5\%$. The unsteady URANS $k-\omega$ SST model is adopted for the turbulence model, while the Zwart-Gerber-Belamry model is adopted for the cavitation model according to [8]. For the analysis, the interval from 0.05 s to 0.35 s was taken as the reference period, thus avoiding the initial unstable phase of the simulation.

The shape and dimensions of the flow domain are shown in Figure 1, and were taken from [15], but here an unstructured mesh was used instead of a structured one.

Figure 1. Flow domain.

The mesh independence test was performed through an iterative analysis of the drag coefficient C_D , the lift coefficient C_L and the pressure coefficient distribution C_p along the profile, which was verified by experimental [18] and compared with numerical results [15], as shown in Figure 2. Five meshes with different cell numbers were considered: M1 with 6000, M2 with 12000, M3 with 26000, M5 with 75000 cells and the finally adopted mesh M4 with 50000 cells. Considering computational resource constraints, the long duration of the simulation and the good matching of M4 curve with experimental results, increasing the mesh density to more than 50k cells mesh is not required. Figure 2 shows the difference between the results of the steady-state and unsteady simulations compared to the experiment.

Figure 2. Distribution of the pressure coefficient C_p along the profile.

With an increase in the number of cells, the unsteady simulation curve on the suction surface of the profile, where cavitation occurs, follows the experimental curve with better matching versus the steady-state simulation curve, which indicates the convergence of the results and confirms the validity of the adopted computational mesh, while in areas of the profile where is no cavitation, the unsteady cavitation curve is slightly shifted higher in comparison to the other two curves.

3. Results and Discussion

Obstruction of the hydroprofile, along with the development of cavitation clouds, is shown in Figure 3 for different angles of attack $\alpha \in \{0^\circ, 2.5^\circ, 4^\circ, 8^\circ, 12^\circ, 16^\circ\}$, and for two chosen timesteps $t_1 = 0.2$ s and $t_2 = 0.22$ s.

Figure 3. Shape of the cavitation clouds at timesteps $t_1 = 0.2$ s and $t_2 = 0.22$ s.

In the initial position, when $\alpha = 0^\circ$, there is no cavitation. With the advancement of the angle of attack from 2.5° to 16° , there is a continuous development and expansion of the cavitating cloud. It arises from a small area at the suction side of the profile, near its inlet, then, as the angle of attack increases, it progressively expands until it fills up the whole domain around the profile's suction side and downstream of the profile at $\alpha = 16^\circ$.

The evolution of the cavitation cloud in two relatively close timesteps $t_2 - t_1 = 0.02$ s implies the intensity of the transient character of cavitation. Furthermore, it is notable that there is a significant change in the geometry and position of the cavitation cloud within such a short time interval, indicating a strong correlation with the local changes in pressure, which could have a pulsating character with strong fluctuations. Figure 4 shows the change in static pressure at a single point P for the angle of attack $\alpha = 4^\circ$ for a time period of 0.3 s. Over such a small time period

of the simulation, no periodic phenomena occur, which is verified by FFT analyses. This type of diagram can also be created for any other angle of attack.

Figure 4. Pressure pulsations in point P for $\alpha = 4^\circ$.

The presence of cavitation and sudden changes in the flow field that it causes have a direct influence on how the pressure coefficient is distributed around the profile.

Figure 5. Distribution of the averaged pressure coefficient C_p on the profile's boundaries for different angles of attack.

That influence is clearly visible when analyzing the averaged pressure coefficient distribution as shown in Figure 5. For the case when the profile is not inclined, i.e. $\alpha = 0^\circ$, the pressure distribution around both the pressure and suction sides of the profile is identical, considering the symmetry of the profile and the absence of cavitation. As the profile inclines, with the rise of the angle of attack, the cavitation cloud starts to develop and expand throughout the flow domain, so that the straight part of the curve of the pressure coefficient distribution along the suction side starts to grow from the inlet towards the outlet. When $\alpha = 16^\circ$, the entire curve on the suction side becomes almost straight, which indicates the presence of cavitation on the whole suction side. The presence of cavitation and its influence on the pressure distribution around the profile directly deteriorates the profile's performance, which is evident in the changes of the lift and drag coefficients. The time-averaged lift and drag coefficients for angles of $\alpha \in \{-16^\circ, -12^\circ, -8^\circ, -4^\circ, -2.5^\circ, 0^\circ, 2.5^\circ, 4^\circ, 8^\circ, 12^\circ, 16^\circ\}$ are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Values of the lift C_L and drag C_D coefficient for different angles of attack.

The drag coefficient C_D increases with a higher inclination of the profile in any direction, while the lift coefficient increases in the case of turning the profile clockwise and decreases when turning the profile in the mathematical positive direction.

4. Conclusion

The goal of the conducted analyses was to show the hydrodynamic characteristics of the NACA0009 profile under cavitating conditions and to present the unsteady effects of cavitation and all other flow quantities that are linked to cavitation, including pressure fluctuations. The results confirm the presence of fast and intensive changes of pressure in the flow domain in a relatively short time, and the unsteady nature of cavitation presented by an intense dynamic evolution of the cavitation cloud, which is in agreement with the results of contemporary experimental and numerical investigations. The described approach can be applied to other profiles that are used in hydraulic turbomachinery as well. The conducted research can give a comprehensive approach towards the design of runners and impellers of hydraulic machinery with the ability to optimize for different working conditions. The results presented in this paper are only part of a much more demanding and comprehensive investigation of the dynamic characteristics of cascade profiles. In subsequent papers, the influence of numerous other flow parameters (such as different cavitation conditions) and numerical simulation approaches will be presented in detail.

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